

Well Number: C01

Sample ID: K

File Name: C:/Users/Operator/Desktop/Guava easyCyte_DATA/Dept of Genome Engineering/MN/GE_2025_003/YFP_BFP.fcs

Well Number: C02

Sample ID: S

File Name: C:/Users/Operator/Desktop/Guava easyCyte_DATA/Dept of Genome Engineering/MN/GE_2025_003/YFP_BFP.fcs

Well Number: C03

Sample ID: N

File Name: C:/Users/Operator/Desktop/Guava easyCyte_DATA/Dept of Genome Engineering/MN/GE_2025_003/YFP_BFP.fcs

Well	Sample ID	YFP/BFP.Percent.UL Percent for YFP/BFP gated by P01.cells.singlets (%)	YFP/BFP.Percent.UR Percent for YFP/BFP gated by P01.cells.singlets (%)	YFP/BFP.Percent.LL Percent for YFP/BFP gated by P01.cells.singlets (%)	YFP/BFP.Percent.LR Percent for YFP/BFP gated by P01.cells.singlets (%)
C01	K	0.02	0.06	99.41	0.51
C02	S	8.74	59.31	6.30	25.65
C03	N	2.09	89.16	0.44	8.30